

2-DOF Observer Based Controller for First Order with Dead Time Systems

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Abstract : This paper realized the 2-DOF controller structure for first order with time delay systems. The co-prime factorization is used to design observer based controller $K(s)$, representing one degree of freedom. The problem is based on H^∞ norm of mixed sensitivity and aims to achieve stability, robustness and disturbance rejection. Then, the other degree of freedom, prefilter $F(s)$, is formulated as fixed structure polynomial controller to meet open loop processing of reference model. This model matching problem is solved by minimizing integral square error between reference model and proposed model. The feedback controller and prefilter designs are posed as optimization problem and solved using Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). To show the efficiency of the designed approach different variety of processes are taken and compared for analysis.

Keywords : 2-DOF, integral square error, mixed sensitivity function, observer based controller, particle swarm optimization, prefilter.

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